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Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter

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The attachment describes the Archaeological site of Pian del Ciliegio (near Manie Plateau, Finale Ligure, Western Liguria, Italy) with interesting findings of petroglyphes near excavation area and the consequent new archaeological implications.

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Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter

(Author: Alfredo Pirondini)

The Archaeological site of Pian del Ciliegio (in Ligurian language: Cian da Séréja) consists of a rock shelter located in the Ponci Valley, near Manie Plateau, Municipality of Finale Ligure (Savona Province, Western Liguria).

The coordinates, obtained with a GPS apparatus are: altitude: 238 m. over the sea level; latitude: 44°12'8,388"N; longitude: 8°22'29,748" E.

The area has evident and many karst features and is characterized by the presence of many rocks, eroded by weathering, consisting of Miocenic bioclastic limestone, rich in fossils: the "Finale Stone".

The karst has led to the formation of a great number of caves and natural cavities, often inhabited by humans until the Palaeolithic, such as "Arma (Ligurian term for Cave) delle Manie", one of the largest in the Finale, which is about 420 meters, as the crow flies, from the considered shelter.

Pian del Ciliegio can be reached along a detour towards south-west, on the left side of the trail (marked with two red squares), which, descending from the Manie Plateau, along the Rio Voze Valley, comes in Ponci Valley (a tract of the Roman road called "Via Julia Augusta", where are the remains of five Roman bridges, three of which well-preserved), near the Third Roman Bridge called "Voze Bridge".

The deviation described above is overrun by vegetation and the Author (the last visit was in January 2011) has restored the access trail, which must pass two dry walls to get to an open space bordered, to the south, by a rock wall where is the rock shelter (Photo 1) and to the left of that, a little cave (No. "F 3" of Cadastre of Ligurian Caves), with dry stone walls (Photo 2).

Currently, the excavation area is protected by railings and is not accessible.

At the base of the entrance of the cave there is a stone roughly squared (about 150 cm wide) at the base of another more massive boulder, with an oriented cruciform (photo 3).

The petroglyph dating is not univocal, but its sharp edges, despite deterioration due to meteoric exposure, suggest an age later than the findings of the nearby shelter: presumably not earlier Iron Age that, in Liguria, developed between 900 and 180 BC.

These rocks, with little cups and other deteriorated engravings, recall the structure of the megalithic altars in the Finale Area (6), (7), (8), (9), (19), typical of Celtic - Ligurian peoples, dated during a period of time from the end of the fifth, to the end of the third millennium BC, including the Neolithic and the Bronze Ages (10), (12), (13), (14), (15), (16).

On the other hand, the cross-shaped, could also be considered a sign of Christianity (Roman - Christian and / or Post-Roman ages) in an area that had a religious function (14), also related to the cult of the dead, as demonstrated by the remains of a tomb found in the shelter area.

We must, however, remember that the whole area was probably visited in ancient times (Palaeolithic), given the proximity to the Arma delle Manie, so the human presence would be documented for a period extremely extended: from the Palaeolithic to this day (1).

The excavations (11) were conducted, following the reporting of unauthorized researches, between the end of 1992 and the summer of 1997 by the Archaeological Superintendence of Liguria

The studies also show that the site was frequented for 400 to 500 years, mainly for the processing and production of clay handmades. Carbon deposits were found related to the remains of stack ovens, pottery fragments, stone artifacts for smoothing pottery.

The storage of these materials, measuring about 40 square meters, is present only in a depression of the ground, produced by the erosion of a stream that led into a sinkhole, then buried. This stream, for the known karst features, later moved to the current bed of Rio Voze.

The analysis of carbon and pollen have allowed to date the findings to the Neolithic (which developed in Liguria from 5800 to 3600 BC) and, more specifically, the period of the "Impressed Ware Culture" (Ancient Neolithic: from 5800 to 5000 BC) and "Square-Mouthed Pottery Culture" (Middle Neolithic: from 5000 to 4200 BC).

The stratigraphy of the site (Fig. 1) attests to a successive frequentations that start from the Ancient Neolithic, with a succession of Anthropogenic levels (beaten, carry-ground beds of ash, and dark grey levels of use, impregnated with organic matter and rich of carbons) and levels of sterile silt, resulting from the effects of flooding of the river in front of the site.

The micromorphological analysis of the studied levels have shown the possible different modes of site frequentation: the presence of coprolites of caprovinic origin and alternation of utilization levels (with ashen and sterile silt layers), corroborate the hypothesis of a seasonal use of the shelter (mainly with animals), with a residential use and production of ceramic tools (as shown by the evidence of clay baking) and also funerary, as evidenced by a burial remain.

The ash layers indicate that the site was cleaned up by fire at the resumption of human presence, from the residues of the previous seasons forages and from materials gathered by the abandonment.

The formation of a soil at the top of the deposit suggests that the site was less significantly frequented, following the documented periods.

Furthermore were reported and identified the remains of charred seeds and fruits, i.e.: cereals (barley, spelt, wheat) and forest resources, such as elderberry, raspberry, hazelnut and wild plum.

There are also numerous acorn cotyledons which could also be used for food.

The radiocarbon dating (11), performed for the levels of the "Square-Mouthed Pottery Culture", is from the fifth millennium BC (between 4700 and 4300 BC approximately).

Archaeometrical investigations (5), conducted with light microscopy and XRPD (X-Ray Powder Diffraction) on samples of "Impressed Ware Culture" and "Square-Mouthed Pottery Culture", suggest different sources of materials and production techniques.

The nature of mineral inclusions indicates, in all cases, local or circumlocal production (longest distance of about 10 Km). The mixtures of the Square-Mouthed Pottery contain, in fact, elements that can be referred to the Paleozoic metamorphic rocks outcropping in the area (with the presence of calcite inclusions) with typical characteristics of other productions of Neolithic pottery from contexts of other caves in the studied area.

In contrast, the Impressed Ware, even if it has been found in more limited quantities, shows a great variability with regard to its composition and origin area.

In fact, besides several local mixtures (with inclusions of metamorphic rocks and the presence of varying amounts of calcite), were also found pastes with ophiolitic (coming, probably, from Tuscany) or volcanic inclusions (originating, likelihood, Central Italy).

These data confirm and complete those of nearby archaeological sites of Arene Candide and Pollera Caves. During the Ancient Neolithic was, presumably, a long-distance movement by sea of men and merchandises (including ceramics).

The finding of a cylinder of clay (11) presenting a surface with series (5x12) of linear incisions, perpendicular to each other, forming 60 square boxes, is remarkable. This is, probably, a "Token" (term that can means "printed sign" or "printed mark", but - archaeologically - means a system of digital recording). In 8 of 60 boxes a point was imprinted before the firing. Presumably, would be an ancient numbering system. Similar findings were discovered in archaeological sites, contemporary to the site in question, especially in the Middle East: this object is unique among the finds of Italian Neolithic.

Discussion

The Neolithic was a decisive period of prehistory: in less than 2000 years of human existence changed more deeply than the 2 million years that preceded it. Many Authors speak of "Neolithic Revolution" because the man, by Binder and Hunter, became Farmer and Breeder, starting the control of natural resources to suit his own

food needs. At the same time, the he began to be settled and this led to changes in a society, which had been devoted to nomadism. These radical changes due, according to some authors (2), (3), (18) to the arrival in Liguria of new people by sea, from Central - South of Italy, or, according to others (4), for economic and technological crisis of local Mesolithic groups, are proven right in the Caves of Finalese (i.e.: Arene Candide, Pollera) and in Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter.

Conclusions

Pian del Ciliegio appears to be an archaeological complex that probably could supply more discoveries in case of investigation resumption, in light of the findings outside the current excavation area. The discovery of petroglyphs and megaliths, demonstrates a larger attendance by the man. Also in the Cave F3 area, not only during the Neolithic, but also in periods before and after this Age (i.e.: Metal Age) until a time very close to ours. I remember that the Manie Plateau and the namesake Arma, were inhabited since the Palaeolithic Age and the human presence is witnessed to this day.

The Finale is therefore a crucial area to understand the developments of the stages of human prehistory and history.

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Photo 1: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter: excavation area

Photo 2: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter Cave (N°. "F" 3 of Cadastre of Ligurian Caves)

Photo 3: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter: oriented cruciform

Photo 4: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter: the Altar in front of cave F 3

Photo 5: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter: the excavation area

Photo 6: Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter: the excavation area

